

Biomedical Engineers / In-House Maintenance Personnel

Socio-demographics

1. What is your age?
2. What is your training?
3. How long have you worked in the hospital / SNCU?

Equipment Routine Maintenance

1. What equipment types in the SNCU / NICU do you perform work to maintain?
2. Do you perform maintenance on a scheduled basis? If yes, what is the frequency schedule?
3. What equipment types in the SNCU / NICU require the most maintenance?
4. What challenges do you face in maintaining equipment? What do you need to perform your work better or more easily?
5. Does anyone else besides you maintain equipment? If yes, who?
6. Is there a record of routine maintenance?

Equipment Repair

1. How do you diagnose problems? Does the equipment display any code, signal, etc.?
2. What equipment types in the SNCU / NICU do you perform work to repair when broken/malfunctioning?
3. Do you have what you need in order to make authorized repairs?
4. What equipment is covered under a service bundle/warranty? Under the AMC (Annual Maintenance Contract)? What equipment is not covered?
5. What are the warranty terms for each type of equipment and how do you keep track of them?
6. What is the process for getting equipment repaired under the AMC? Who notifies the AMC?
7. Do you collect any data on repairs? (i.e., equipment failures, frequency of calls, time it takes to initiate a repair, and/or any other indicators)
8. How would you rate the service the hospital facility receives from the AMC providers/maintenance technicians (quality/timeliness/responsiveness)?

0 - Other/no response

1 - Poor 2 - Fair 3 - Good 4 - Very good 5 - Excellent

9. Are there ever any additional costs associated with repairs? What would those costs be for?
10. If a piece of equipment cannot be repaired, what happens?
11. What are the most common failures with each type of equipment?

Equipment Procurement

1. How do you get new equipment? Who makes decisions about how, when, and what should be procured? What is the overall timeline?
2. When, if ever, is equipment transferred between facilities? Does the AMC transfer with the equipment?

3. How much of the equipment is donated? By whom? Does the equipment come with an AMC?
4. If there is new equipment, do you receive training on how to maintain it? Who provides the training?
5. If there is new equipment, do you install it or support its installation in any way?
6. Are there any other positive or negative aspects of receiving new equipment?
7. Who is responsible for the order and management of consumables?

Additional Questions

1. How do you receive training on each equipment you are responsible for? (Do you receive training on the job, training from an institution, or training via the distributors?)
2. What could be done to make your job better and easier?
3. Do you use any Standard Operating Procedures, checklists, or other information around the NICU / SNCU? Who is responsible for signage and postage?
4. How often do you rely on equipment alerts and alarms (red lights, beeps)? What are your positive experiences with these functions? What, if any, challenges do they create?
5. Who is responsible for ordering replacements such as consumables and accessories for the equipment? From whom? Where do you store consumables and accessories for each piece of equipment?
6. Do the consumables, accessories, and spare parts come with clear installation/information guides?

Recommendations to improve equipment processes:

1. What recommendations do you have for improving the management of equipment in the NICU / SNCU?
2. Do you have anything else you would like to add?

Thank you for your participation!